

Quantifying barriers of urban mobility

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ABSTRACT

Barriers in cities, such as administrative boundaries, natural obstacles, railways or major roads are thought to induce segregation. However, the empirical knowledge about this phenomenon is limited. Here, we present a network science framework to assess barriers to urban mobility along their hierarchy, across residential areas and visited amenities. Using GPS mobility data, we construct a network of blocks from the sequence of individual stays in a major European city. A community detection algorithm allows us to partition this network into non-overlapping areas of dense mobility clusters, in which the effect of transportation hubs can be tuned with a parameter. We apply the Symmetric Area Difference index to quantify the overlap between these mobility clusters and the polygons of urban area separated by barriers. Reducing the effect of transportation hubs results in smaller scale mobility clusters that fit better to lower rank administrative or road barriers compared to their higher rank pairs. We find that characteristic urban barriers can replace each other in dividing mobility clusters of different scales. Next, we define the Barrier Crossing Ratio, the fraction of barrier crossings that link mobility clusters. An event study of bridge closure demonstrates that the Barrier Crossing Ratio can capture barrier effects even on small spatial scales. The decomposition of this indicator by origins and destinations suggests a significantly higher impact of barriers on those who live closer to the city center and smaller impact on visits to complex amenities. These results contribute to the ongoing discourse on urban segregation, emphasizing the importance of barriers to urban mobility in shaping interactions and mixing.

1. Introduction

Mixing people is essential for cities' economic progress; yet, most interaction happen within neighborhoods (Jacobs, 2016). Residential segregation is known to worsen economic opportunities and health outcomes of the poor (Chetty et al., 2016; Roux, 2001), is associated with high crime levels (Sampson & Raudenbush, 1999), and has been found to hinder economic growth of cities (Li et al., 2013). Building on recent developments in urban mobility research that leverages high resolution location data retrieved from mobile devices (Alessandretti et al., 2020; González et al., 2008; Schlöpfer et al., 2021), segregation inquiry is increasingly moving to understand mixing beyond residential areas. This literature has documented in detail that social mixing varies by locations and amenities in the city (Athey et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2020; Fan et al., 2023; Juhász et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2018; Yabe et al., 2023) and is influenced by mobility policies (Abbiasov et al., 2022; Nilforoshan et al., 2023). However, the role of urban barriers, despite

their direct impact on mobility (Jin et al., 2021), has remained an unsolved puzzle.

Major roads are great examples of this puzzle, as these were built to increase accessibility, but roads connecting distant places can be obstacles for local mobility (Jesus & da Silva, 2022). Research in "Road Ecology" investigates the impact of roads on wildlife (Coffin, 2007), and has led to different types of mitigation measures in the last decades to reduce the number of roadkill, including building tunnels and bridges for mammals (Villalobos-Hoffman et al., 2022) or amphibians (Helldin & Petrovan, 2019). The barrier effect (also known as "community severance") is also examined in human environments, but are mainly conducted via surveys (Anciaes & Jones, 2020; Emmanouilidis et al., 2022; Jesus & da Silva, 2022) and focus on a specific part of a city (Jesus & da Silva, 2022; van Eldijk et al., 2020). Major roads are obstacles of local interaction (Aiello et al., 2025) and further characteristic physical barriers like railways, parks or rivers are natural borders between neighborhoods (Park & Rogers, 2015) and can also amplify segregation

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by hindering mixing and interaction across separated areas (Ananat, 2011; Tóth et al., 2021). However, the questions of which barriers limits mixing, where in the city and for whom, have not been answered.

In this paper, we contribute a network science framework to evaluate the role of barriers in urban mobility. The basis of the approach is a widely used community detection procedure that, in our case, groups together locations by maximizing the density of mobility flows within groups (Blondel et al., 2008; Fortunato & Newman, 2022). Compared to other approaches that evaluate barriers by analyzing mobility for pairs of locations, community detection reveals clustering relationships among locations acknowledging that individuals often are present in more than two locations during the day and their mobility flows contains more than one network edge (Jin et al., 2021). Unlike the widely applied gravity approach that estimates probability of mobility across barriers, community detection on spatial networks identifies clusters of high probability mobility events and can reveal the role of barriers by analyzing how clusters of such complex mobility flows fit to these boundaries. The method can be fine-tuned to decrease the impact of large mobility hubs and increase the importance of local mobility flows that can help find the scales of clustered mobility links that have the best fit to urban barriers (Alessandretti et al., 2020; Expert et al., 2011).

The method is demonstrated with an empirical exercise based on a GPS mobility data set that contains 161,294 mobile phone devices in Budapest, Hungary over 6 months before and 6 months during the COVID-19 pandemic, which had a big impact on urban mobility and segregation across the globe (Napoli et al., 2023). From the geolocation and time-stamp of pings, we construct a mobility network, in which nodes are blocks where individuals spent at least 15 minutes and edges are weighted by the number of individual mobility events between the blocks during the day. We first assess the role of various administrative and physical barriers as obstacles to mobility with a gravity model. Next, we run the Louvain community detection algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) on the mobility network that helps us identify dense mobility clusters. By increasing the resolution parameter of the algorithm, we mitigate the dominance of mobility hubs and group blocks into clusters of relatively smaller sizes. Then, we identify polygons of residential areas bounded by characteristic barriers and calculate the Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) indicator that is a global indicator to quantify how mobility clusters align with boundaries. Finally, we compute the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) to capture the relationship between mobility events across urban barriers and detected mobility clusters that can be decomposed by origins and destinations. This procedure and the novel indicators enable us to quantify the impact of urban barriers on mobility across the hierarchies of barriers, across small and large spatial scales in cities, and across residential locations and visited amenities.

We first show that the impact of barriers has intensified during the COVID-19 pandemic. Then, we find that administrative barriers, rivers, and roads significantly decrease mobility but their impact varies across the city. Increasing the resolution parameter, we observe an improved alignment – measured by the SAD indicator – with lower rank administrative barriers and secondary roads, while the fit with higher rank administrative boundaries and major roads improves only up to a certain point. We demonstrate that this is due to a shift among barriers: as we mitigate the role of transportation hubs, characteristic urban barriers replace each other in dividing mobility clusters. Next, an event study of a bridge closure is used to illustrate how barrier crossing is captured by the BCR indicator on a small spatial scale. This is followed by an analysis on the scale of the entire metropolitan area, in which we decompose the BCR indicator by home locations and find that the impact of barriers depends on the residential areas and visited amenity locations. Mobility clusters of urban dwellers fit to all barriers significantly better than the mobility of residents who commute to the city from its agglomeration suggesting that barriers have a higher effect on local mobility than on those that link distant places. The measure also implies that barriers are not likely to impact mobility to amenities that are rarely found elsewhere in the city, except the river that is the most significant

boundary of mobility. Repeating the exercise for Nagoya, Japan using a distinct data set, we find that fitting the mobility clusters to higher versus lower level urban barriers can reveal general patterns across cities. However, the method is also able to show differences that we show by contrasting barrier impact by home location.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data

Our GPS mobility data were collected by a data aggregator company and consist of the location coordinates and time stamp of pings generated by unspecified smartphone applications. The data covers whole Hungary but we limit the analysis to mobility events in Budapest. Our observations contain 135,271 devices in Budapest that we aggregate to a 6 months period starting from September 2019 and 35,894 devices that we aggregate to a 6 months time window starting from November 2020 that contains the second and third waves of COVID-19 contagions in Hungary (see Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Section S1).

To capture barriers, we apply the openly available OpenStreetMap data for Budapest that contains polygons of rivers, railroads, and hierarchies of administrative boundaries and roads (Fig. 1d). As for the administrative boundaries, administrative level 9 (districts) and 10 (neighborhoods) is utilized. Budapest has 23 districts and 207 urban neighborhoods. Note that neighborhoods are in between districts and census tracts in the spatial hierarchy. The OpenStreetMap classifies the roads based on their hierarchy. For this study, primary and secondary roads are considered, motorways are merged with the primary roads, since they cannot enclose areas on their own. Secondary roads are less important than primary roads in the OSM highways hierarchy and they limit smaller areas than primary roads. The primary roads divide the city into some larger parts, and with the secondary roads into smaller parts. A script was developed to create polygons from the city parts enclosed by the roads, for details see Section S3 in the Supplementary materials.

2.2. Network generation

We construct a mobility network that connects blocks, polygons bounded by lower order roads, across the city following two steps. First, we identify blocks where individuals spend at least 15 min by a stop-detection algorithm (Aslak & Alessandretti, 2020) that clusters the ping sequences of single mobile phones in space and time (Juhász et al., 2023). This stop-detection method can detect the stationary points of individual movements and cluster pings around locations, where the individual stopped. Some applications – e.g., navigation – leaves frequent traces leaving a continuous trajectory, but other applications generated sporadic traces. To ensure meaningful stop-detection, the analysis is restricted to those mobile phones that have at least 20 pings, similarly to (Juhász et al., 2023). The algorithm gives each stop a label indicating a place that can reoccur along the trajectory of the user. This procedure has enabled us to identify home locations by detecting stops between the 8 pm-8 am hours. To restrict the analysis to Hungarian residents, following (Juhász et al., 2023), we limit the analysis to users whose home location can be identified on at least 10 days. In the BCR exercise, we further limit the observations to those users who have home locations in Budapest or in municipalities in the Budapest agglomeration.

In the second step, we link those blocks that individuals visit subsequently during the day and generate a network in which the edge weight is the number of individual mobility flows over a 6-month period, either before the COVID-19 pandemic (see a representation of this network in Fig. 1a) or during the COVID-19 restrictions. The places are considered only within a day because of the sporadic nature of the data. It is undesired to connect a user's last position of a day to the first position of the next day. Naturally, a threshold could be introduced as if a user is active in the night, a valid mobility trajectory is broken at

Fig. 1. Illustration of the mobility network and the research problem. The observed mobility network (a), where the node sizes are proportional to the degree of a node and the colors represent the detected communities at resolution 2.5. The “layers” of the barriers (d) analyzed in the study include relatively rare natural (river) and built (railways) barriers and relatively frequent ones that also have hierarchical orders like roads (primary and secondary roads) or boundaries administrative urban units (districts and neighborhoods). Mobility clusters detected with resolution parameter $\gamma = 2.5$ (b, e) and $\gamma = 5$ (c, f) compared to administrative boundaries (b, c) and to roads (e, f).

midnight. This, however, is a possible direction of future enhancements.

2.3. Gravity model

To enable comparison with traditional approaches, we first apply a gravity estimation (Krings et al., 2009) that is a widely used method for activity distance and border effect measurement (Jin et al., 2021). Originally, the gravity model for mobility flow is formalized as: $Mob_{ij} = k \frac{P_i^\alpha P_j^\beta}{r_{ij}^\gamma}$, where Mob_{ij} is the mobility between spatial unit i and j , P_i is the population in unit i , and r_{ij} is the distance between spatial units i and j , and k , α , β , and γ are constant parameters (Jin et al., 2021).

The original formula is extended with the number of crossed barriers. When counting B_{ij} the crossed barriers between two blocks, the beeline is considered between the centroid of the block as the mobility data does not contain any information about the way of transport. So, every barrier is counted – by type – which the straight crosses. As for the distance (r_{ij}), the haversine (great-circle) distance is used between the two block centroids. The model (1) was evaluated using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. The barrier variables B_{ij} have been inserted separately to the regression model due to their high correlation.

$$\log Mob_{ij} = \alpha \log P_i + \beta \log P_j + \gamma \log r_{ij} + \delta B_{ij} \quad (1)$$

2.4. Community detection

The gravity approach has limitations in capturing the full complexity of mobility networks that can be important since mobility during the day

typically include more stops that can form triangles, and more complex patterns. Here, we apply a widely used community detection method on the mobility network that can provide new insights by detecting dense mobility clusters that contain most of the mobility events and can represent silos of highly likely mobility links. We use the Louvain algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) that partitions nodes by maximizing the modularity index that is calculated using the formula (Eq. (2)).

$$Q = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij} - \gamma \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \right] \delta(c_i, c_j), \quad (2)$$

where A_{ij} is the weight of the link between block i and j , k_i is the sum of the weights of links of block i , c_i and c_j denote the community of blocks i and j , δ is equal to 1 if $c_i = c_j$ and zero otherwise and m is the sum of the weights in the network. Increasing the resolution parameter $\gamma > 0$, one can get smaller communities, while a small γ provides large communities. In our mobility network, this procedure mitigates the role of flows between large mobility hubs and enables the emergence of local mobility clusters. Previous research has shown that community detection on spatial networks forms spatially segregated partitions (Expert et al., 2011; Grauwin et al., 2017; Lengyel et al., 2015; Sobolevsky et al., 2013) and increasing the resolution parameter has been applied to partition labor mobility networks into occupations with similar skill requirements (Adam et al., 2018) and also to find the scale of administrative boundaries that fragment commuting networks across cities (O’Clery & Kinsella, 2022).

However, detecting the role of barriers in urban mobility networks requires further analyzes, since a variety of boundaries may hinder

mobility and thus partition the network, while their impact may differ across the city in non-trivial ways. In our Budapest case, for example, administrative barriers define communities in the Northeastern part of the city where major roads have seemingly no impact on the community structure at $\gamma = 2.5$ and $\gamma = 5$ (Fig. 1 e and f/marker 1). Marker 1 denotes a community that fits to the District 15 in both resolutions but is also crossed by freeway M3, a multilane road with physical separation from its surrounding that connect downtown of Budapest to cities in East Hungary. On the contrary, a major road separates mobility communities in the Southeast of the city (Fig. 1/marker 2). The bright green community, denoted with marker 2, does not fit to administrative boundaries but is perfectly limited by the freeway M5 and by the river Danube. Finally, physical and administrative boundaries might align, as we see in the case of District 21 in Budapest (Fig. 1 b, c, e, f/marker 3). This district that is depicted by marker 3 is bounded by the river Danube and its fork and thus, it constitutes a community in the mobility network not only at the two displayed values of the resolution parameter but in further settings too (see Supplementary Section S5 for details). Note that the features of a physical barrier can affect its community-forming power as Fig. 1 shows: lower order roads (displayed by dotted lines) seem to have no impact on communities at lower resolution, but higher order roads do (e.g., Fig. 1/marker 2 or 3). As expected, the communities detected with higher resolution parameter are smaller. However, this trend is more true in the downtown, while communities with the markers 1–3 remained almost the same.

We propose two indicators to evaluate how administrative and physical boundaries fragment mobility networks by quantifying the fit of mobility clusters detected by the Louvain method at various levels of the resolution parameter. Due to the nondeterministic nature of the community detection algorithm, both measures are calculated for $n = 10$ iterations of the community partitioning for all decimal values of $\gamma \in [1, 10]$. The stability of the community detection across executions was examined using Cramér's V, which can be found in the Supplementary Section S2. Then, the mean and standard deviation of the barrier indicators are calculated across of the different community partitions.

2.5. Symmetric Area Difference

The Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) index, SAD_γ captures the lack of overlap between the polygons defined by mobility clusters and the polygons delineated by characteristic urban barriers for every resolution γ (Fig. 2a). Formally,

$$SAD_\gamma = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{p,q} (A_{p_r} \cup A_{q_r}) \setminus (A_{p_r} \cap A_{q_r}), \quad (3)$$

where A_p and A_q are the area sizes of the overlapping mobility cluster polygons p and urban area polygons q and n is the number of iterations of the Louvain community detection at resolution γ . Lower values of this index mean a better fit of the detected mobility clusters to urban boundaries.

To confirm that the increasing resolution parameter of the Louvain community detection algorithm produces not only smaller communities but the partition converges to urban barriers, the similarity of the communities and the enclosures had to be measured. The area of the blocks clustered as a community, but outside the target polygon (e.g., district or enclosure) and the area of the target polygon that is not covered by the community is summarized as a measure. In other words, the area of the false positive and the false negative blocks, which is the symmetric difference of the two polygons (Fig. 2a).

The changes in the community areas are evaluated in respect of the administrative and infrastructural barriers during the change of the resolution parameter with the symmetric area difference between the clustered blocks (i.e., community) and the administrative districts.

2.6. Barrier Crossing Ratio

Next, we define the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) index, BCR_γ measures the relationship between those mobility events that cross barriers and those that cross barriers and detected mobility clusters as well (Fig. 2b). We calculate the fraction of barrier and cluster crosses among all barrier crossings, and take the inverse of this ratio. This indicator is formalized by

$$BCR_\gamma = \frac{1}{n} \frac{\sum_m CB(M_k^i, U)}{\sum_m (CB(M_k^i, U) \times CC(M_k^i, C_\gamma))}, \quad (4)$$

where m is the total number of mobility edges, CB is a binary function that evaluates to 1 if M_k^i , the k^{th} mobility edge from block i , crosses an urban barrier U and 0 otherwise, while the function CC takes the value of 1 if M_k^i crosses mobility clusters and n is the number of Louvain iterations at resolution γ . Since the number of barrier crossings is constant, a decreasing value of the indicator along increasing γ signals that border crossings align with mobility cluster crossings. This is because CC is increasing as the communities become smaller.

Fig. 2. Illustration of indicators used to assess the fit of detected mobility communities to urban barriers. The Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) (a) measures the sum of the areas that are not overlapping between detected mobility clusters and the areas delineated by the given barrier. The Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) quantifies the fraction of those trips that cross barriers and mobility clusters as well among all barrier crossing movements (b).

3. Results

Using the SAD indicator, we first compare the role of higher- versus lower rankings of physical or administrative barriers. This is followed by an illustration of the substitution across barrier types as we go from large to small mobility clusters. Next, we test the applicability of the BCR indicator in an event study of a bridge closure that captures barrier effects on small spatial scales. Then, we investigate whether those who commute or travel from further away are less likely to be affected by barriers. We finally complement the analysis by checking how visited locations differentiate the barrier impact.

3.1. Assessing the community fit to urban barriers with Symmetric Area Difference

To present a benchmark for urban barrier assessment, we first investigate their impact on urban mobility by testing a widely-used gravity model, in which the volume of mobility flow between block i and j is estimated by their Euclidean distance, the sum of their incoming and outgoing flows and the number of barriers between them (for more details see [Materials and methods](#)). We find that river Danube has the strongest impact on mobility and railways have the weakest ([Fig. 3a](#)). Further, there are barriers that have hierarchical relations within the category, such as administrative boundaries can be defined at the higher rank of districts or at the lower rank of neighborhoods; while roads can be primary or secondary. In the gravity model, we find no clear pattern whether higher or lower rank barriers in these hierarchies have a stronger impact on mobility. While boundaries of districts have a bigger impact than neighborhood borders, the coefficient of secondary roads is stronger than that of primary roads. Yet, the gravity model measures an average impact of barriers disregarding the locations of mobility links. On the contrary, a network of mobility links is denser in the center of cities. By finding smaller scales of mobility clusters in high-density areas, our approach provides a better way to understand hierarchies of barriers because we can fit mobility clusters to lower-rank administrative barriers too.

Indeed, assessing the fit of mobility clusters to urban barriers with the SAD_γ indicator, we find that barrier hierarchies have a more intuitive imprint on mobility than in the gravity model. As γ increases in its low ranges, SAD_γ decreases for both district and neighborhood boundaries ([Fig. 3b](#)). However, the fit to district boundaries reaches a maximum at higher values of γ , while to the fit to neighborhoods further improves as the algorithm finds smaller and smaller groups of blocks that tend to

represent mobility clusters at the scale of neighborhoods. A similar trend is found in terms of road hierarchies: as γ grows, community detection fits to primary and secondary roads, but at high values of γ the technique provides an improving fit to the secondary roads only ([Fig. 3c](#)).

Comparing the period that precedes the COVID-19 pandemic with the period that contains the second and third waves of the virus diffusion, the increasing coefficients of the gravity model inform us about an increasing impact of all types of urban barriers on mobility ([Fig. 3a](#)). However, according to the SAD indicator, the fit of detected communities gets worse for both levels of administrative boundaries and for secondary roads as well. The worsening fit during the pandemic might be due to the drastic drop of mobility links (ca. 33 % of the links are present). However, the growth of SAD values at given γ values are not drastic. In the case of primary roads, one can observe that the fit does not differ between the two periods at $\gamma > 3.5$ that also includes the best fit we find. Thus, the community detection method provides stable results for primary roads across very different periods in terms of mobility habits.

In the case of primary roads, we find a characteristic level of the resolution parameter ($\gamma \approx 4$) that provides the best fit of communities. Up to this resolution parameter, the fit measured by SAD_γ improves but the fit gets worse at higher values of γ . This optimal fit arises due to local mobility clusters that emerge after we decrease the dominance of mobility links between large transportation hubs by increasing γ (see [Eq. \(2\)](#)). The differences in the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) between the pre-pandemic and the pandemic period can be found in [Section S10](#) of the Supplementary Information.

Analogously to the pre-pandemic–pandemic comparison, the workday–holiday differences were evaluated ([Section S7](#) of the Supplementary Information). We found that the barrier effect is smaller for every barrier type on weekends and holidays than on workdays. The reason of this could be that the holiday network has fewer edges than the workday network, because people tend to travel less during weekends and holidays, and visit fewer locations ([Pintér & Felde, 2021](#)).

3.2. Replacement of barriers in local mobility

A potential explanation of the worsening fit in [Fig. 3c](#) can be that local mobility events cross primary roads. However, it may also be that the role of a certain barrier weakens because another one replaces it. Indeed, [Fig. 4](#) illustrates an example where such a replacement happens using the case of marker 1 in [Fig. 1e](#). The fit to the administrative boundary of District 15 is weak at $\gamma = 1$ when the mobility cluster covers

Fig. 3. Barrier effect on urban mobility in the gravity and the mobility network approach, preceding and during COVID-19 restrictions. The coefficients of ordinary least squares (OLS) regression measure barrier impact on flows between two locations (a). In (b, c), the lines and shaded area represent the mean and the 95 % confidence interval of the Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) indicator as a measure of barrier fit of mobility clusters detected in ten iterations of the Louvain method for every γ . The improving fit to administrative boundaries along the increasing resolution parameter (b) signals that lower-rank boundaries tend to align with local mobility clusters. This is the case for secondary roads as well but the optimal fit to primary roads at $\gamma \approx 4$ suggests that emerging local mobility clusters are less bounded by primary roads (c).

Fig. 4. The process of community fitting to District 15 and inset figures show the Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) in respect of the resolution. Note that the largest intersecting community at $\gamma = 1.0$ (a) is about twice as big as the district. As the resolution increases the community matches the district boundary (b, c), which loses the community forming power at about $\gamma = 6.0$, as the M3 motorway gradually cuts in half the community (d-f).

a relatively large area (Fig. 4a) but becomes reasonably good in the range of $\gamma \in (3; 6)$. Further increasing the parameter, we find that the smaller scale mobility cluster fits to the administrative border in the south but is limited in the north by the major road that cuts the district into two. The local mobility cluster is bounded by a combination of barriers that worsens the fit of a single category and suggests that it is not just single barriers that impact mobility but they can influence mixing in more complex configurations.

The fit of mobility clusters to the railways and the river can be found in Supplementary Section S6. The fit of railways during COVID restrictions quantified by SAD_γ is of the same level with districts or primary roads but fits worse at large γ in the pre-COVID period. The SAD_γ values of the fit to the river decrease as γ increases.

Repeating the analysis on a distinct data set from Nagoya, Japan (Pintér, 2024; Yabe et al., 2024), we find that the SAD_γ indicator describes the role of administrative barriers in urban mobility similarly (see Supplementary Section S12). By increasing the resolution parameter γ , the fit of mobility clusters to administrative barriers improves, while it is significantly better for lower-rank boundaries for all γ .

3.3. Barrier Crossing Ratio during bridge closure

Based on a community initiative, the Liberty Bridge in Budapest was closed to vehicles on the weekends in July 2019, allowing people to use the bridge for recreational activities. For example, yoga and dance classes were held or people simply used the bridge for a picnic. This event serves as a case study to analyze the barrier effect in a small-scale, local setting. The observation area is downtown Budapest (marked in light blue in Fig. 5a). Including the two bridges at the northern and

southern borders of downtown the selected area contains 5 bridges.

Trips that began and ended within the observation area on weekends in July 2019 were selected separately for analysis. For comparison, trips on the weekends in June 2019 were selected in the same way. Then, BCR was calculated following the procedure but only for the he river Danube as a barrier (Fig. 5). As expected, the barrier effect is stronger (the BCR is lower) when the bridge was closed. The first weekend of July 2019 resulted the strongest effect, presumably because it was the first such event of the year. On the other hand, the second weekend of June 2019 also shows a stronger barrier effect, which may have been caused by the reduced traffic due to the 3-day holiday weekend. (June 9 was Pentecost in 2019, a holiday along with the following Monday.)

Calculating the same BCR values for the whole city shows no difference between the June and July weekends (Fig. 5c), which means that the effect of closing a bridge is strong locally, but less striking at the city level. Moreover, the BCR values are generally higher, indicating a weaker barrier effect. This result aligns with the finding of another study (Janosov et al., 2021), which examined the effect of closing the Chain Bridge (for maintenance) to the public transport.

3.4. Barrier Crossing Ratio by residence

Urban barriers might have a divergent impact on neighborhoods as individuals daily mobility depends largely on the locations of work, schools, and services that are unevenly distributed in and around cities. Thus, in the next step of the analysis, we assess the role of barriers in mobility by decomposing the set of individuals by areas of residence and by visited amenities. To do that, we leverage the home locations of individuals identified in (Juhász et al., 2023) by the device location during

Fig. 5. The boundaries of the observation area in light blue, and the Liberty Bridge (a). Figure b shows the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) evaluated for the weekends of June (pink) and July (green) 2019. The lower BCR for the July weekends indicates a stronger barrier effect due to the closed Liberty Bridge. Figure c shows the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) evaluated at the city level for the same period and shows that the increased barrier effect remains at the local level. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the 8 pm–8 am daily periods and the amenity portfolio of stop locations measured in the same paper. As many people commute from the agglomeration to the capital (Pintér & Felde, 2022), not only the inhabitants of Budapest are taken into consideration, but people living in the larger agglomeration as well. We use the urban area definition of Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO) to distinguish seven district groups within the city of Budapest and sort municipalities into six sectors of the Budapest agglomeration to group home locations (Hivatal, 2018) (visualized in Fig. 6a). Then, we use the mobility network across Budapest blocks described in Fig. 1 to quantify the tendency that individual mobility events cross urban barriers and detected mobility clusters, using the Barrier Crossing Ratio (Eq. (4)) that can be decomposed by origins and destinations of mobility events.

We find a striking difference between the BCR indicator of those dwellers who live in the city and those who live in its agglomeration (Fig. 6). In every barrier category, agglomeration sectors have higher BCR values than sectors of the city, indicating that commuters from the agglomeration cross relatively more urban barriers without crossing boundaries of mobility clusters than residents of city sectors do. Except the river, the value of BCR is above 1 for agglomeration sectors for the lowest γ values in the case of all other barriers. This indicates that the number of total barrier crossings is higher than those crossings that are across barriers and mobility clusters at the same time. Increasing γ provides a better fit of mobility clusters to barriers, in which the differences between urban and agglomeration sectors are stable as γ grows.

Thus, the detected mobility clusters fit urban barriers better for those who live close to these actual barriers than for those who live farther away. Naturally, people living in the agglomeration have different mobility patterns than urban dwellers: their vast majority use cars when commuting to the city but also optimize home and work location so that they usually commute to the closest part of the capital. For example, people living in the Northwestern sector visit mostly North Buda and only a small portion of their visits are located in the inner Eastern Pest (see the sectors in Fig. 6a and Supplementary Section S9 for details). However, North Buda and South Buda behave like agglomeration sectors at low levels of γ in the case of Primary roads and Railways but perform a relatively good fit to barriers at high γ .

The Danube as barrier has the strongest impact on mobility. Interestingly, the ratio of barrier crossings and mobility cluster crossings is

nearly constant across values of γ for most sectors, meaning that local mobility flows hardly cross the river. In other words, crossing the river almost automatically means crossing mobility clusters too. This is especially true for residents of the agglomeration: 90 % of their crossings over the river leads to other mobility clusters. The Supplementary Section S8 contains further analyses in respect of the residence-based mobility networks, including another evaluation of the BCR where separate networks were generated for the urban areas. This approach takes into consideration that commuting distance impacts mobility patterns that can be captured by different mobility networks. Yet, these results also confirm that urban barriers in Budapest have a stronger impact on urban dwellers than on commuters.

Interestingly, we see a different pattern for Nagoya (Supplementary Section S12) where we could evaluate the fit of mobility clusters to municipality boundaries and primary roads using the BCR_γ index. Residents of the city have higher BCR_γ values suggesting that they cross urban barriers that are also barriers of mobility clusters more often than residents of agglomeration towns. Thus, local contexts have an important role in distinguishing the impact of urban barriers on dweller groups that further research should focus on.

3.5. Individuals Barrier Crossing Ratio by home locations and amenity mix at destinations

Finally, we calculate the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) indicator for individuals, instead of areas. Since the mobility network is aggregated from individual trips, one can compare the barrier and mobility cluster crossings at the individual level in the same ways as it is introduced in Section Barrier Crossing Ratio. The individual Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) captures the average BCR of individual citizen c in the n^{th} run of the community detection with resolution γ . The indicator takes a lower value for those individual citizens who cross barriers by visiting mobility clusters and takes a larger value for those who cross barriers without leaving the mobility cluster.

This measure enables us to investigate how the role of barriers depends on home locations and also on visited amenities in a multivariate analysis. We regress BCR with an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression, using the formula:

Fig. 6. Barrier effect based on the users' home location groups. The HCSO defines seven district groups in Budapest and six sectors of the agglomeration (a). From the Budapest mobility of the inhabitants of these areas, thirteen networks were built and evaluated for all barrier type with the BCR_γ index and increasing the γ parameter (b).

$$\log BCR_{\gamma,n}^c = \alpha + \beta_1 \log D_c + \beta_2 \log AC_j + \varepsilon, \quad (5)$$

where D_c is the geographical distance of the home location of citizen c from the city center and AC_j is the complexity of amenity portfolio of the visited j location as proposed by (Juhász et al., 2023) and ε is the error term. Amenity complexity is high in those locations that host diverse services that are difficult to find elsewhere in the city. Locations with complex amenity portfolios have been found to promote social mixing because they serve a diverse demand and can attract visitors from the whole city (Juhász et al., 2023).

The findings reveal significant relationship between the distance, amenity complexity and Barrier Crossing Ratio that also seems to be stable $\gamma > 1.5$ for all types of barriers (Fig. 7). As expected, D_c correlates positively with BCR (Fig. 7a) confirming our previous finding that those who live farther away from the center are more likely to cross barriers without crossing mobility clusters because the fit of the detected cluster is worse for them. However, we find a negative correlation between AC_j and BCR for most types of barriers. This result suggests that visiting complex amenities that are in other mobility clusters, individuals usually cross urban barriers too. The river seems to be an exception here as well, but as discussed above, there are rarely any mobility clusters that extend across the river; thus, BCR calculation in this case could only consider visits to two islands that are sharing mobility clusters with districts on the Pest side. The stable coefficients of D_c and AC_j over γ signals that relationship with BCR is not an artifact of community sizes; instead, these correlations capture a general impact of barriers on mobility, considering complex structures of mobility networks. The OLS tables are in the Supplementary Section S11.

4. Discussion

Urban barriers are obstacles of social interactions and even the built urban infrastructure, which is aimed to facilitate access, can hinder mobility. Here we apply a network science framework that provides a new understanding of this phenomenon and enables us to investigate how urban barriers delineate clusters of mobility considering complex network structures. Our results demonstrate that besides natural and administrative boundaries, major roads within cities can separate individuals. We explore that mobility clusters can be impacted by combinations of barrier types. We also discover that barriers have a smaller impact on mobility to complex amenity locations because these places attract visits from many neighborhoods. In the case of Budapest, urban barriers better align with mobility clusters of urban dwellers and less so for residents who live in the larger metropolitan area and commute to the city. However, we find a different pattern in the case of Nagoya, where barriers have a bigger impact on commuters. Thus, the question

of why the barrier impact come to be and how it differs across groups of citizens is open. Further research should therefore investigate the role of local economic environment, the transportation system, commuting trends, social segregation, and urban geography in general to better understand what makes urban barriers impact mobility.

The strong impact of barriers has wide-ranging implications for the ongoing discussion of social mixing in cities (Athey et al., 2021; Bokányi et al., 2021; Fan et al., 2023; Juhász et al., 2023; Moro et al., 2021). Similarly to the role of mobility restrictions that have been documented to increase urban segregation (Napoli et al., 2023; Yabe et al., 2023), urban barriers can hinder the mixing of individuals from various socio-economic strata, even if they live only on the opposite sides of roads or railroads (Ananat, 2011). Such separation can foster segregation in social networks, (Aiello et al., 2025) and can lead to growing inequalities (Tóth et al., 2021). Therefore, the impact of barriers on mobility should be considered in recent proximity-based urban developments - that are often referred to as the 15-min city concept - that aim to foster short distance active mobility and inclusion in cities. We need a better understanding how improving access to amenities (Abbasov et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020), which are reachable with active mobility, can overcome urban barriers like major roads that still channel the flows of larger distance car traffic.

Our results contribute to an ongoing discussion that focuses on quantification of barriers in urban mobility and social interaction. The approach used here is similar to Jin et al. (Jin et al., 2021) that determines the thickness of the barrier, expressed in meters, which measures the activity distance increased because of the barrier. However, instead of ‘thickness’, we express the barrier effect in relative frequency of crossing (Barrier Crossing Ratio) and distinguish three types of barriers: natural (river), infrastructural, and administrative barriers, but in multiple levels (roads and administrative border evaluated in hierarchy). Unlike Aiello et al. (Aiello et al., 2025) that examines the impact of urban highways on online social interaction with spatial randomization of the edges, we develop measures based on urban barrier crossing and network clustering of mobility traces. Our bridge closure case study is comparable to Van et al. (van Eldijk et al., 2020) that examines the consequences of placing a motorway and a railway in tunnels for the accessibility of certain amenities.

Our study is not without constraints that are partly due to data limitations. Although the available dataset covers 2 years, most of this period is affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Mobility restrictions in 2020 and 2021 limits monthly comparisons across years and consequently, seasonal variations in the barrier effect would have been difficult for us. We encourage future research to address this niche. On the other hand, differences between workdays and holidays are provided in Section S7 of the Supplementary Information.

Also, as the mobile positioning data used in this study does not have

Fig. 7. Urban barrier impact on individuals by distance from the center and by visited amenities. We depict the relationship between Barrier Crossing Ratio and the distance between the inhabitants home location and the city center (a) and the mean location complexity of the visited places (b). Solid lines represent estimation coefficients and the shaded are denotes standard errors.

information about the means of transport, it is not possible to differentiate between pedestrians, bikers, public transport passengers or car drivers. A possible future direction is to use additional data sources, e.g., from bike sharing services, to analyze the barrier effect on bikers. Such advances could help improve the bicycle lane infrastructure and detect possibly dangerous spots that behave string barriers for bikers. Using further data from public transport usage could help us understand how public transport contributes to the emergence of mobility clusters. Future work should investigate the circumstances of community formation in mobility networks across a variety of cities, including small towns compared to the largest metropolitan areas that have polycentric structures. We think that our method is capable of capturing barrier effects across scales, which is due to the resolution parameter in the community detection algorithm. Moreover, the framework should work in different urban contexts as well. Yet, it is an empirical question, how barriers impact urban mobility across cities that have various spatial structures for reasons of differing natural environment, historical and cultural background. For example, a river on the edge of the city might have lower impact while water barriers between coastal city centers and their nearby islands might be strong. The proposed method should be able to capture such cases, but we need further research to provide insights.

Section S12 in the Supplementary Information demonstrates an application of the method to the YJMob100K dataset, which covers the Nagoya metropolitan area (Pintér, 2024). It is a larger area including two bays: Ise and Mikawa Bay. In this way it also introduces different city structures, and at the same time it includes multiple towns, although the road network does not form communities in the case of YJMob100K dataset.

To highlight the separation power of built infrastructure, we also have to compare different trajectories of urban evolution that has led to the dominance of administrative boundaries or, on the contrary, to the dominance of roads in delineating mobility clusters. Many times, the built environment can be captured by forms different from the barriers we analyze in this paper. Dense residential neighborhoods, parks, malls, or industrial areas can be barriers of mobility. We discuss how our method can be extended to polygon barriers in the Supplementary Information S4. In mono-centric cities, mobility, measures of street network topology, and density of buildings are correlated with the distance from the center, but this is different in polycentric cities. Thus, the question of how the role of barriers change in centers and subcenters and away from them should be analyzed in more urban contexts and in polycentric cities too.

Finally, we need further research that focuses on mixing of strata across urban barriers and the types of mobility that can decrease experienced segregation given the boundaries in cities.

Although there is a plethora of network partitioning algorithms, and a related discussion on the advantages and disadvantages of these methods, evidence suggests that the Louvain algorithm is one of the most robust ones (and the most efficient one) (Yang et al., 2016). Furthermore, spatial extensions of the Louvain algorithm can also incorporate the role of geographical distance in the network null model of the partitioning process (Expert et al., 2011), which can be a subject of follow-up research.

Thinking of the built environment as barriers is not new at all in the urban planning literature and practice. In many US cities, the deconstruction of urban highways has been a tool to foster healthier mobility across neighborhoods, to mitigate segregation and to establish livable a urban environment (Stehlin, 2023). Our study shows that a variety of urban barriers impact mobility by not just influencing single mobility events but also by fostering mobility clusters on both sides of the barriers. Urban planners should therefore consider these complex structures of mobility when they aim to facilitate barrier crossings helping accessibility by public transport, walking or biking (Matos & Lobo, 2023). Similarly, while planning new transportation and travel lines, the mobility networks should be analyzed to avoid the barrier effects

(Nilsson & Delmelle, 2020; Tehrani et al., 2019). In such cases, forecasting the benefits of establishing crosswalks or bringing railways underground should consider impact on local versus long-distance mobility and the features of mobility destinations since these matter for barrier crossings.

Abbreviations

BCR	Barrier Crossing Ratio. 3, 4, 7, 8, 10–16
GPS	Global Positioning System. 2
HCSO	Hungarian Central Statistical Office. 12, 13
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares. 5, 9, 15
OSM	OpenStreetMap. 4
SAD	Symmetric Area Difference. 2, 7–11

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gergő Pintér: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Balázs Lengyel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2025.106322>.

Data availability

The observed mobility networks are available in GitHub (github.com/pintergreg/quantifying-barriers-of-urban-mobility) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14869888>). However, the raw mobile positioning data is not publicly available.

The barrier data is obtained from OpenStreetMap; these data are copyrighted by the OpenStreetMap contributors and licensed under the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL).

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